

**Children born of conflict-related sexual violence
Toolkit for analysis of the legal & policy framework**

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INTRODUCTION

Objective:

This toolkit should be used to conduct a review of the strengths and weaknesses of the legal & policy framework with regard to challenges faced by children born of conflict-related sexual violence (CBoCRSV). *Note:* This will include issues faced by children in general in the country, but with a compounded impact on CBoCRSV.

How to use the Toolkit:

1. Confirm list of key issues potentially faced by CBoCRSV (see sample challenges in **Table 1.**)
2. Identify legislation and policies that directly reference CBoCRSV and/or impact their well-being. Compile the information into **Table 2, Column A and B**
3. As you complete the table, analyse the strengths and gaps of existing laws and policies and synthesize these in **Table 2, Columns C and D.**
4. Consider how completely and effectively the laws and policies are implemented (including weaknesses in bodies responsible for delivering). List any gaps in **Table 3.**
5. When the information has been compiled, synthesize it into the actions required in **Table 4.** This will become the basis for developing your action plan to address weaknesses in the legal and policy framework and its implementation.
6. Produce summary report based on the assessment, to include key issues, strength/weaknesses and recommendations for next steps.

I. KEY OBSTACLES FACED BY CHILDREN BORN OF CRSV (CBOCRSV)

The below table describes typical issues faced by CBoCRSV and how the legal and policy framework can positively and/or negatively impact on these. Please amend as needed for the context. Also note any factors contributing to the problem that could be resolved through law or policy.

TABLE I

	Key issues	Description of how framework impacts	Any contributing/linked factors
1.	Legal Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to register birth - Ability to convey nationality/statelessness - Legal exclusion (eg from war victims' identification) 	
2.	Belonging (stigma)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to family support/counselling - Access to family-based/alternative care - Access to psychosocial support - Reintegration of children born into armed groups 	
3.	Discrimination (stigma)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to access schooling (registration/fees) - Ability to access healthcare (documentation/fees) - Ability of children born into armed groups to integrate into the community 	
4.	Economic marginalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to social support - Inheritance rights 	
5.	Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion in transitional justice processes/mechanisms - Inclusion of children in peace processes 	
6.	Safety & basic needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strength of protection system - Access to food, shelter, water, etc. 	
7.	Others?		

II. ANALYSIS OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND RELEVANT SYSTEMS

Complete the assessment below, using information from relevant legislation, policies, government commitments and secondary documents. The assessment should include reference to Concluding Observations of any human rights bodies or institutions (eg, the Committee on the Rights of the Child).

Compile the information generated into Table 2A (laws and policies) and Table 2B (international instruments) below.

TABLE 2A

Law or Policy	Questions/Description of relevance	Strengths	Weaknesses/Gaps
[Child rights law or policy]	Right to be heard in decisions/issues affecting them? Mechanisms and/or formal structures for participation (eg., child parliament)? Accessibility to marginalised children? <i>Note: Some of the questions below might be answered in an overarching child-focused law or policy.</i>		
[War victims law?]	Are survivors of sexual violence and CBoCRSV recognised as victims of the war? Are they entitled to special status and/or reparations? Under what conditions?		
[Criminal Law]	Criminalisation of rape? Forms of violence, exploitation & abuse against children that are prohibited?		
[Family Code] Civil Code Civil Procedure Code	Requirements for registering a birth? How is nationality conferred? Parental rights and obligations? Paternity & patrilineal recognition? Rules/practices around adoption, kinship care, institutionalisation?		
[Child protection law/policy]	Procedures/systems to identify children at risk? Reporting obligations? Identification of most vulnerable? Obligations on parents/caregivers to protect children from violence, abuse and neglect? Formal		

	child protection system defined in the law?		
[Social protection law/policy]	Social protection measures to support vulnerable children and their families? What type? What conditions? Are families of CBoCRSV able to access these measures? Are CBoCRSV able to receive this support directly and, if so, from what age? Do any criteria for receiving support have the potential impact of excluding CBoCRSV or their families?		
[Constitution]	Non-discrimination provision? Automatic incorporation of international treaties?		
[Education law/policy]	Obligations for attendance, age of attendance? Cost? Bullying? Grounds for exclusion? Non-discrimination principles?		
[Health law/policy]	Requirements for receiving care (costs, birth registration, etc. and waiving these? Confidentiality provisions? Is mental health support included? Non-discrimination principles?		
National Plan of Action/Law on SGBV?	Are survivors and CBoCRSV included? What support/programmes are included? Reparations?		

TABLE 2B

Other instruments	Commitments	Actions/Gaps
Convention on the Rights of the Child	Reservations? Concluding observations of CRC Committee and NGO alternative reports – and government response?	
Call to Action/Framework Promoting the Rights and Wellbeing of CBoCRSV	Has the country endorsed the Call to Action? Have they made commitments under the Framework?	
Regional human rights instruments	Other instruments ratified?	

Paris Principles & Commitments on Children associated with armed forces and armed groups	Reintegration support? Does include children born of sexual violence in an armed group?	
Others?		

IV. DEVELOPING A PLAN OF ACTION

Based on the weaknesses identified in the tables above, identify the key changes needed and what steps to be taken to implement these.

TABLE 4

	Dominant problem	Contributing factors	Necessary response	Action plan to address
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				
5.				
6.				
7.				

V. SUMMARISING COLLATED INFORMATION

Using the information in the tables above, develop a summary report that can be used for further advocacy and action planning. The report should be concise, use non-technical language and provide clear entry points for action.

Sample report outline:

1. Executive summary (including key findings, priority recommendations and a roadmap for implementation)
2. Introduction (including background, context and methodology)
3. Voices of lived experience (realities faced by CBoCRSV in the context)
4. Legal and policy landscape (summary of framework, including constitutional, criminal law/justice, civil/family law, reparations, etc)
5. Key challenges identified (barriers faced that can be addressed through law, policy & practice reform)
6. System implementation gaps identified
7. Priority action areas
8. Implementation roadmap